

PI-PREFORM & JOINT REVOLUTIONARY IMPROVEMENT FOR FASTENER-LESS COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

A composite bonded Pi-joint is a means of joining two substructures of a component together without the use of fasteners. The Pi-joint gets its name from its semblance to the Greek letter Pi (π). The joint offers the potential for making bonded unitized aircraft structures which are strong, durable, lightweight and resilient when damaged. 3D woven pi-preforms currently provide a baseline method for achieving robust adhesively bonded joints in composite aircraft structures. However, the cost of 3D woven pi-preforms is prohibitive for numerous applications that would benefit from high performance adhesive joints. The Lockheed Martin team identified and have been investigating alternative Pi-configurations using oriented ply stacks for improved performance and cost of fastener-less structures with Pi-joints. This paper discusses two material and process selections including discontinuous fiber prepreg such as Toray Torayca® ET40 and non-crimp dry fabric/resin infusion such as Hexcel HiMax® IM8/1078-1 for making high-quality pi-preforms and initial joint performance up to 2X in shear and marginal changes in pull off vs. the 3D woven baseline. The latter was selected for application in a bulkhead subcomponent manufacturing demonstration in the near future.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Pi joint geometry has provided robust mechanical performance needed in bonded composite assemblies, particularly in bonding webs to skins. The Pi-joint gets its name from its semblance to the Greek letter Pi (π). Multiple OEMs employ woven Pi preforms on flight vehicles such as Lockheed Martin's section of Sierra Nevada's Dream Chaser. Currently, 3D woven Pi preforms, infused with polymer resins, provide the baseline method for manufacturing adhesively bonded joints in composite aircraft structures (Fig. 1). The cost of these infused Pi preforms, which are manufactured with strict 3D weaving parameters, followed by film infusing in epoxy or BMI resins, is prohibitive for a number of applications that would benefit from such high-performance adhesive joints. Additionally, critical aerostructures (e.g., wing, fuselage, bulkhead) comprising Pi-shaped joints are made through time-

intensive co-bonding operations, which will need to address for further cost/rate improvement.

The formation of a pi-shaped composite preform is difficult to achieve due to the abrupt geometric features inherent in its design. 3D woven pi-preforms have been used in their manufacture and have demonstrated desired combinations of shear and pull-off strength performance. The cost to manufacture the 3D woven pi-preforms using state-of-the-art automated weaving and/or braiding technologies has remained high in spite of extensive studies.

This paper discuss the systems and methods of an innovative solution [1, 2] which provides technical advantages over previous pi-shaped preform technology, including (i) reduced manufacturing cost compared to 3D woven pi-preforms [3, 4]; (ii) improved shear strength; and (iii) flexible configuration and excellent formability enabled by either (1) discontinuous, aligned fiber prepreg that allows creation of complex shaping of the pi-shaped preforms from individual components with desired layups while maintaining mechanical properties or (2) dry continuous fiber material such as non-crimp dry fabric and subsequent infus with a resin. Commercially available material systems were selected to demonstrate the concept of manufacturing the new pi-preforms and resulting joints. Pull-off and shear tests were performed to assess the joint performance.

Figure 1: Schematics of 3D woven pi-preform (A), the resulting pi-joint (B), and location of pi-preform used in a model bulkhead subcomponent

2 METHODS AND MATERIALS

2.1 Preform Design

Fig. 2 shows a schematic of a new pi-preform design [1, 2] comprising the following components: L-angle x 2, U-shape x 1, Joint Base x 1, Noodles x 2 and optional Adhesive. The L-angle, U-shape, Joint Base comprises oriented ply stacks of a formable and drape-able material to void wrinkles. Some selected design parameters were noted for optimal joint performance, manufacture-ability and cost/rate including (1) material form enabling forming without wrinkles, (2) ply thickness and stack up producing the overall component's thickness, (3) noodle construct, and (4) adhesive.

2.2 Material Selection and Joint Manufacturing

Firstly, Torayca® ET40 prepregs [5] were chosen to demonstrate the pi-preform design in bonded joints for cost/rate and performance versus those made from a 3D woven Pi-preform. ET40 material is made from a parent unidirectional prepreg where slits are introduced at designed locations for drape-

ability and extension to conform to tight geometries while maintained equivalent modulus and about 80% strength as its parent material. The resulting ET40 prepreg also offered similar handle-ability as its parent. It was documented that matrix chemistry changes showed no impact on the effectiveness of the ET40 process. Several ET40 materials were selected, comprising combinations of two fibers (T800, T1100), 3 epoxy resins, 1 BMI resin while fiber areal weight (FAW) ranged from 70-192gsm and resin content (RC) ranged from 33-40%. The baseline material for development was AMS6891 material (T800S/#3900, 191gsm, 35.5% RC).

ET40 material was used to form the 2 L-angle, 1 U-shape, and 1 Joint Base on respective machined aluminium mandrels, then these components were assembled together with one of the three noodle options and no adhesive, resulting in a 3-foot-long preform stick. Each component was made from a symmetric and balanced ply stack of ET40 prepreg that was laid up flat and formed into shape using a heated mandrel, with the exception of the noodles. The process for fabricating each Pi-Preform was as follows:

- *Layup*: Using precut plies of ET40 prepreg material, flat symmetric and balanced flat charges were laid up and debulked for two minutes every four plies.
- *Forming*: The flat charges were then formed by hand over heated mandrels with the backing left on. Once the charges maintained the shape without being held in place, the charges were bagged and debulked against the heated mandrel for five to ten minutes. Mandrels were heated to 120°F – 140°F during the forming process.
- *Geometry check*: Each component was checked for critical geometry against a “Go-No Go” gauge to verify the component had held the correct shape after forming.
- *Assembly*: Components were assembled together using 3D printed assembly jigs and metal tooling that helped locate each component relative to the others. Once all components were in place, a final heated debulk was used to form the individual components into a single Pi-Preform. The heated debulk was done at the same temperature as the forming step.

Throughout the process of forming, as well as assembly, each component was visually inspected for any wrinkles that developed as a result of the forming or placement process. The ET40 material showed no issue with wrinkling while bending up to 180° around a 2mm radius.

Several materials were used for the noodles in the ET40 preforms. Most consisted of industry standard uni-directional prepreps shaped before assembly and then co-cured with the Pi assembly. Several other materials / designs were evaluated, verifying earlier work showing increases in pull-off strength.

A 3-foot-long preform stick was used to join a precured center rib and skin made from legacy composite prepreps. The assembly was bagged and cured in an autoclave at 350F x 120min for the epoxy systems and 375F x 120min cure, with a 440F x 240min oven post cure for the BMI system, producing 3-foot-long T-panels as shown in Fig. 3. The T-panel was machined into 4.5- and 2-inch-long coupons for shear and pull off testing, respectively.

Secondly, Hexcel HiMax® IM8/1078-1 system [6] composed of Non-Crimp Fabric of 300gsm fiber areal weight and knitted into a bi-axial sub-laminate including a binder veil were selected to assess further cost/rate improvement in one-shot infused pi-joints. Hexcel HiMax® NCF has several benefits when it comes to performance and processing. HiMax® is constructed with multilayer UD blankets, a 20 dTex fine stitch, and V100 thermoplastic (TP) veil at each interleaf, acting as a binder holding the compacted plies together with minimal bulk after forming (<5% @ 60%FVC) and in its 3D shape. The V100 TP veil also increases damage tolerance (CAI / G1C) performance.

The non-crimp fabric IM8 material was used to form designated laminate ply stacks into the L's, U, and Joint Base on respective machined aluminium tools, summarized in Fig. 4. A vacuum forming process was utilized to shape and de-bulk this material close to its final position. At room temp all the plies were placed over a tool and draw vacuum and as the bag collapsed, the material was shaped into position over the tool and debulked. While maintaining vacuum, the bagging and tool were heated above veil melting temperature (120°C), and held as long as necessary to ensure all plies had reached the melting temperature. After this, the part was cooled down to room temperature with vacuum still applied,

and then the finished part was removed from the bagging in 3D shape.

The preformed L-angle components were attached to the cure tools with adhesive band, along with peel ply or release fabric, and the Center Rib was inserted into the U-shape and secured. Bringing the cure tools together to squeeze the Center Rib + U-shape formed the Pi-preform geometry. Filler materials (noodles) were inserted into the triangular spaces on either side of the U-shape at the bottom of the assembly, then the Joint Base was placed either on this assembly and then on the Skin below. Peel ply and distribution media were placed depending on the infusion strategy required. Once complete, a vacuum bag was applied to the complete dry 3-foot-long assembly with shaped, supportive tooling with inlets and outlets for infusion, then 1087-1 resin was infused at 176F into a 248F tool through the laminate with vacuum. The use of NCF reinforcement greatly aides the Z-direction permeability, allowing the resin to saturate the thickest areas of the Pi joint. Once infusion was complete, the resin temperature was raised 356F and cured completely in 120min, producing the 3-foot-long T-panel. The T-panel was machined into 4.5- and 2-inch-long coupons for shear and pull off testing, respectively.

Figure 2: Schematics of a new pi-preform comprising oriented ply stacks of 1 Joint Base (1), 2 L-angle (2), 1 U-shape (3), 2 noodles (4), and optional adhesive (5)

Figure 3: Schematics of a joint construction for each of the two material types, showing the new pi-preform joined to center rib and skin (Left) and the final 3-foot-long Pi-preform stick (Right)

Figure 4: HiMax® material summary (Left) and schematics of forming components of the new pi-preform (Right)

3 Joint Characterization and Testing

The 3-foot-long T-panels were inspected using Laser-UT (ultrasonic inspection) prior to machining into test coupons (Fig 5). Joint pull-off and shear tests were performed on Instron machines using the fixtures shown in Fig. 6 at a rate of 0.05"/minute to failure. Polished joint coupon cross-sections were inspected under a microscope to document microstructure and anomalies.

Figure 5: T-panel (A), shear (B) and pull off (B) coupons made with Pi-preform comprising ET40 uni-tape (70gsm) and “film adhesive” noodles. Precured web (vertical) and skin (flat) joined by Pi preform with a film adhesive.

Figure 6: Joint test coupon loading in test fixtures

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 7 shows the machined joint coupon and microscopic cross-section images of the joint made from ET40 material. These materials and sound fabrication practices resulted in robust processing of high-quality T-panels. The resulting joint showed controlled cured ply thickness as expected, limited ply waviness, and no porosity. Test results achieved 132% pull off and 225% shear versus an equivalent baseline joint made from 3D woven pi preform. Joint performance varied with matrix and noodle toughness and changes in ply thickness (joint weight). Pull-off strength varied most with toughness characteristics and shear strength increased with laminate design.

It was noted that the cost from the laboratory manual process would be similar to the baseline. However, it was anticipated that the cost would be about half if customized fabrication tools were used, and a target of one-quarter the cost if utilizing automated, mechanized forming workstation was developed.

Future efforts may utilize a reduced degree of cure for the structural laminate(s), center web and skin in a first cure cycle, offering a balance in handle-ability during the joint assembling process and bond-ability after a second bonding cure cycle. This may provide process span and cost reductions. These options will be explored and confirmed in future studies.

Figure 7: Images of machined joint coupon and its cross-section made from a ET40® material.

Figure 8 shows the machined joint coupon and microscopic cross-sections of the joint made from HiMax® IM8/1078-1. A robust processing method was developed for T-panels after a couple of trials. The resulting joint showed variable cured ply thickness as expected, more ply waviness than the ET40 version, and some resin richness at the bottom of the U-shape due to fitting gaps, all of which will be address in the next iterations. Test results achieved 91 % pull off and 225% shear versus a baseline joint made from 3D woven pi preform of similar thickness.

It was noted that the cost from the studied manual process would be similar to the baseline. However, it was anticipated that the cost would be even lower than the ET40 version if automated forming would

have been employed. Furthermore, this one-shot infused joint could offer additional performance benefits for both shear and pull off if stitches would have been employed in addition to optimized stacking sequences and material options. Further studies will explore this approach at both element and bulkhead sub-component (Fig. 1C) levels.

Figure 8: Images of machined joint coupon and its cross-section made from HiMax® IM8/1078-1.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

It was shown that new Pi-preform design opened opportunities to leverage lower cost materials via advanced fabrication techniques in oriented ply stacks versus expensive 3D woven materials. Manufacturing feasibility was successfully demonstrated with both Torayca® ET40 prepregs and Hexcel HiMax® feedstocks. Further improved manufacturing rate and cost is anticipated with automated preforming process and will be explored in future studies.

Currently, both options achieved about 2X higher in shear strength and marginal changes in pull off strength versus the baseline 3D woven. While optimized stacking sequences and material options could improve performance further in both options, the one-shot infused joint option provided an opportunity to explore additional performance benefits with stitching at critical areas of the dry assembly prior to resin infusion. Future studies will investigate this stitching approach with one-shot infused element joints and a bulkhead subcomponent.

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